

ZrN coating as a source for the synthesis of a new hybrid ceramic layer

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

ZrN/MAO coatings
Coefficient of friction
Wettability
Corrosion
Wear

ABSTRACT

The study focuses on an innovative process for the use of a ZrN coating on Ti6Al4V alloy for orthopaedic bone implants. The preparation process combines the technology of physical vapour deposition (PVD) and micro-arc oxidation (MAO) to achieve hydrophobic properties, improved corrosion resistance and enhanced coating adhesion to Ti6Al4V alloy. An alkaline electrolyte and different microarc discharge intensities were used to prepare MAO coatings. The evaluation of the structure and topography of the coatings was performed using SEM with XRPD, EDX, and XPS analysis. The prepared oxide coatings Zr, ZrSiO₄, and ZrTiO₄ increase the corrosion potential depending on the applied source frequency and thus increase the corrosion resistance of the hybrid system. At the same time, the formation of oxide phases leads to changes in surface topography associated with increasing friction coefficient and better wear resistance.

1. Introduction

Despite their low wear resistance in clinical practice, titanium alloys are still among the most commonly used orthopaedic and trauma implants, especially Ti6Al4V [1]. For these reasons, implant surfaces are modified using micro-arc oxidation (MAO) [2] or physical vapour deposition (PVD) [3] technologies.

PVD coatings with high hardness, excellent corrosion resistance and better abrasion resistance include transition metal nitrides [4]. For example, the stoichiometrically well-synthesizable ZrN represents a thermodynamically stable phase with attractive functional surface properties [5]. The properties of these coatings can be improved with the deposition of multilayered metal nitride systems using the cathodic arc evaporation (CAE) technique, which also allows one to create adhesion functional layers [6].

A more efficient option available for achieving improved corrosion and abrasion resistance properties of Ti6Al4V is the preparation of a hybrid system using a combination of PVD and MAO techniques [7]. By

applying the MAO method, porous oxide layers can be achieved, doped with elements (such as Ca, P, Na, Si, C) of the electrolyte used. Thus, this technique allows for an effective influence on the tribological properties of the prepared layers, namely in reducing the coefficient of friction (COF) compared to the substrate [8]. In a preliminary study by Gabor et al. [9], it was shown that a hybrid system combining Ti and TiZr PVD layers with subsequent MAO application allows the preparation of porous oxide layers with improved corrosion resistance, increased abrasion resistance and lower coefficient of friction than the substrate or PVD layers alone. The hybrid modification also allowed the elimination of undesirable elements in the surface layer (Al, V) and improved the biocompatibility of the Ti6Al4V alloy.

Commercially available coatings for orthopaedic implants include single [10,11] or multilayer ZrN coatings [12,13], which are used for articulating surfaces in joint arthroplasty. The standard methods used for ZrN deposition include the CAE method [14]. ZrN-coated implants commonly exhibit defects such as droplets or holes in the surface, which can lead to abrasive wear of the coating [15]. In the work of Herbster

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apsadv.2024.100615>

Received 20 February 2024; Received in revised form 20 May 2024; Accepted 28 May 2024

Available online 7 June 2024

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et al. [16], individual coated systems on knee implants were compared, with identification of the defects present, critical factors and possible causes associated with clinical practice. The results confirm that ZrN coatings exhibit a range of defects, including micro-scratches and surface discolouration. Delamination of the ZrN coating and the presence of pitting defects were also confirmed [16].

Oxidized zirconium alloy (OxZr) [17], which can also provide an anti-allergic effect, may be promising for wider use. These alternative coatings are used in 8-10% of total knee arthroplasty cases.

In this study, a combination of MAO and PVD techniques using ZrN PVD layers under different MAO discharge conditions was used in an attempt to detail the newly formed ceramic layers. The aim was to demonstrate the possible use of the combination of these techniques for the formation of hybrid oxide layers resistant to wear and corrosion with the prospect of applying the new synthesis to form ceramic phases for their use in orthopaedic bone implants or other technical fields.

2. Experimental

2.1. Preparation and characterisation of layers

The Ti6Al4V alloy substrate samples (Fig. 1a) with a diameter of 15 mm and a thickness of 2.6 mm were surface polished using an HV 20 tubular vibrator (OTEC, Germany) with the use of KF 10 plastic bodies before the ZrN coating was applied. The power of the tub vibrator motor was 1.3 kW with a wet finishing process time of 16 h. Prior to the deposition of the PVD layers by CAE in a Hauzer Flexicoat 850 PVD unit, the substrate surfaces were cleaned by Ar ion bombardment for 20 min. To achieve adhesion, a submicron layer of Ti was deposited on the Ti6Al4V alloy using a Ti target (99.99 % purity) for 20 min at 320 °C. The ZrN monolayer (Fig. 1b) was deposited using a zirconia target (99.99 % purity) by CAE in the PVD unit for 120 min at 350 °C. The working pressure in the PVD unit was maintained at 10^{-3} mbar with a current of 80 A and a bias voltage of -100 V.

The Ti6Al4V alloy with ZrN PVD coating was subsequently treated using MAO at different pulse source frequencies. For 20 min at 500 V, the ceramic layers were prepared in an alkaline electrolyte (14 g/L $\text{Na}_2\text{SiO}_3 \cdot 9\text{H}_2\text{O}$; 8 g/L NaOH; 100 g/L glycerol) under micro discharge conditions with pulse frequencies of 48 Hz (ZrN/MAO/2, Fig. 1c), 95 Hz (ZrN/MAO/4, Fig. 1d) and 222 Hz (ZrN/MAO/6, Fig. 1e). The pulse size used for all samples was 0.5 ms. The pulse gap widths were 20 ms (48 Hz), 10 ms (95 Hz), and 4 ms (222 Hz). The bath containing the electrolyte was stirred and cooled to 22 °C during the process.

Surface topography, chemical composition, and layer thicknesses were evaluated using a JEOL JSM-7610F Plus scanning electron microscope (JEOL, Japan) with a connected dispersive X-ray spectrometer (EDS, ULTIM MAX 65 mm^2 , Oxford Instruments, England). Layer thickness analysis was performed from 7 different locations and evaluated using AZtec software (Oxford Instruments, England). The samples were mechanically machined to prepare the cross section, which was ground (#400 and #800 grit SiC) and then polished (#1200 grit SiC). After mechanical operations, the samples were cleaned in acetone using ultrasonication for 10 min. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) analysis of the surfaces was performed on an ESCA PROBE (Scienta

Omicron Technology GmbH, Germany) using monochromatised Al K α X-rays (1486.6 eV). Detailed high-resolution spectra were obtained at a constant PE of 30 eV with a measurement step of 0.1 eV for Zr 3d, N 1s, O 1s, Si 2p and C 1s. Phase analysis of coatings was carried out by powder X-ray diffractometry (XRPD) under CoK α irradiation using the Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer (Bruker AXS, USA) equipped with a fast position sensitive detector V \AA NTec 1. The phase composition was evaluated using the database PDF 2 Release 2020. Surface roughness characteristics were measured with the Talysurf 50 profilometer (Taylor Hobson, England). Surface topography was measured using the atomic force microscope (AFM, NenoVision s.r.o.). The contact angles of the distillate water were recorded using an Attension Theta optical tensiometer (Biolion Scientific, Finland).

2.2. Tribological and corrosion analysis

The tribological properties were tested using pin-on-disc tribometers (CSM Instruments, Switzerland) in rotational and linear configurations. In both cases, Al_2O_3 balls with a diameter of 6 mm were used as counter bodies. The samples and balls were cleaned with acetone prior to testing. To simulate the environment of the human body, we performed tests in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS). This solution was prepared by dissolving a Sigma-Aldrich PBS tablet in 200 ml of distilled water and contained 10 mm phosphate buffer, 2.7 mm KCl, and 137.0 mm NaCl with pH 7.4 at 25 °C.

The normal load used during the test was 2 N, and the linear sliding speed was 50 mm/s for each test. The tests on both tribometers were performed twice on each sample. The number of laps for the rotation test was 5000, and the radius of the track was 4 mm. For the linear test, the number of cycles was 2500 with an amplitude of 5 mm. This ensures that the number of passes of the ball through the track is the same for both tests. The friction coefficient μ was calculated from the ratio of the tangential friction force and the normal force. The surface of the Al_2O_3 ball, the surface of the wear track after the tests, as well as the width of the wear track, were analysed using a DSX1000 digital microscope (Olympus, Japan) after the test. The wear track profile was analysed using a Talysurf Series 2 contact profilometer (Taylor-Hobson, United Kingdom). The specific wear rate was calculated from the equation:

$$k = \frac{V}{Fs}$$

where k is the specific wear rate, V is the wear volume, F is the normal load, and s is the sliding distance. The wear volume was obtained by multiplying the area of the wear track cross-section from the profiler measurement and the length of the wear track.

The adhesion test was performed with the Revetest Scratch Xpress+ scratch tester (CSM Instruments, Switzerland). The Rockwell diamond tip (radius 200 μm) was used as an indenter. The scratch test load was set to increase linearly from 1 N to 30 N along the 3 mm scratch with a linear speed of 10 mm/min. The results of the tests were analysed by DSX1000 digital optical microscopy (Olympus, Japan).

The corrosion resistance of the samples was tested in a three-electrode configuration of the measuring system (VoltaLab PGZ 100 potentiostat) over an area of 0.5 cm^2 in an isotonic physiological

Fig. 1. Surfaces of prepared samples: (a) Ti6Al4V; (b) ZrN coating; (c) ZrN/MAO/2; (d) ZrN/MAO/4 and (e) ZrN/MAO/6.

solution. In this measuring system, the samples are connected as a working electrode, a saturated calomel electrode as a reference electrode, and a carbon rod as an auxiliary electrode. The initial potential of the potentiodynamic measurements was set to -150 mV versus open circuit potential (OCP) after stabilisation of the corrosion equilibrium with a polarisation rate of 5 mV/s.

2.3. Statistical analysis

The statistical analyses were carried out using minitab® 17 statistical software. One-way ANOVA with Tukey's test at statistical significance $p < 0.01$ was used for the statistical evaluation of key surface parameters. Results are presented as mean \pm standard deviation (S.D.). Data visualisation was performed in OriginPro 8.5 (OriginLab Corporation, USA).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Characterisation of topography and surface thickness

Fig. 2 shows the characteristic topography of the different applied surface technologies, which included mechanical operations (Fig. 2a), PVD (Fig. 2b) and subsequent final MAO treatment of the ZrN coating (Fig. 2c,d,e). It can be seen that the application of MAO results in an increase in the structure porosity, including micropores and pancake structure, with increasing frequency of the respective pulse gap [18]. This phenomenon corresponds to the total plasma discharge energy and the amount of melt released, which flows to the surface through the discharge channels to form a rapidly solidifying oxide layer.

Elemental mapping (Fig. 3) confirmed that the used source frequency of 48 Hz does not allow the deposition of homogeneous Zr-containing layers due to the insufficient energy used to prepare the oxide layer, where the process of dissolution of the layer with its subsequent destruction is applied. On the other hand, increasing the source frequency for the ZrN/MAO/4 (95 Hz) and ZrN/MAO/6 (222 Hz) samples results in the oxidation of the surfaces with the formation of typical characteristic pancakes with the presence of Zr.

In addition to chemical composition, micro/nano topography is a crucial parameter of coatings for biomaterials. Visible structural changes occur in all MAO coatings (Fig. 4), and in agreement with the measured roughness values (R_a , R_z), it can be concluded that the increase in surface roughness correlates with the size of the applied pulse gap or with the applied frequency (Fig. 5). The formation of MAO coating with structured micro/nano topography is related to the melt recrystallisation during rapid cooling in electrolyte environment and has a significant effect on the adhesion of mesenchymal stem cells [19]. The ANOVA

Tukey test showed that all samples except the substrate and ZrN coating are statistically significantly different regarding the roughness parameters evaluated. The highest roughness was achieved for the ZrN/MAO/6 sample at the applied frequency of 222 Hz.

The presence of Zr corresponded to the applied power of the switching source in accordance with the selected exposure time (20 min). This is related to the most significant increase in coating thickness for the ZrN/MAO/6 sample (14.19 ± 0.92 μm) in the presence of the Zr phase in the outer layer (Fig. 6e,f). The same fact was observed for the ZrN/MAO/4 sample with an outer layer thickness of 9.09 ± 0.52 μm due to the lower discharge intensity applied at 95 Hz (Fig. 6c,d). For the ZrN/MAO/2 sample, the presence of Zr in the MAO coating was not determined, which can be explained by insufficient discharge for oxidation of the Zr phases. Using the lowest frequency (48 Hz), the ZrN layer was destroyed due to the electrolyte used and the oxidation of the Ti6Al4V substrate (Fig. 6b).

The thicknesses of the corrosion-resistant inner layers are given in Table 1; for each MAO layer, they are statistically indistinguishable. For all oxidised samples, substrate oxidation was confirmed with an increase in layer thickness related to the amount of molten substrate according to the source frequency used. As the layer thickness of each sample increased, diffusion of the split ions from the electrolyte to the substrate interface occurred through the subsequent formation of pores and defects on the oxidised sample surfaces. MAO technology enables the formation of a uniform inner layer and a highly porous outer layer.

3.2. Structural behaviour of ZrN and MAO coatings

The presence of nitride phases was not confirmed in any of the MAO coatings. It can be concluded that the oxidation of the nitride phase and gas evolution occurred during the MAO process (Eq. 1). Hybrid layers were prepared on Ti6Al4V substrate by a combination of PVD and MAO methods, the XRD recordings of which are shown in Fig. 7. The qualitative representation of the compounds present in the electrolyte conditions contain SiO_3^{2-} . The representation confirms the rutile and anatase crystalline phases (Eq. 4). On the other hand, silicon oxides (Eq. 5) are mainly represented in the MAO layer in an amorphous form [20] and therefore were not identified using the XRPD technique (Fig. 6). The presence of zirconium was confirmed both in the oxide form (Eq. 7) and in the crystalline tetragonal structure of ZrSiO_4 (Eq. 8) after reaction with amorphous SiO_2 . The presence of the ZrSiO_4 phase indicates the possible use of the MAO technique for controlled synthesis and formation of a layer with enhanced oxidation resistance and thermal stability [21]. Furthermore, the orthorhombic phase ZrTiO_4 was identified in the XRD spectrum, which is formed by the reaction of Ti and Zr oxides (Eq.

Fig. 2. SEM of sample surfaces (a) Ti6Al4V; (b) ZrN coating; (c) ZrN/MAO/2; (d) ZrN/MAO/4 and (e) ZrN/MAO/6.

Fig. 3. Elemental mapping of MAO coatings.

Fig. 4. 3D view of sample surfaces: (a) Ti6Al4V; (b) ZrN coating; (c) ZrN/MAO/2; (d) ZrN/MAO/4 and (e) ZrN/MAO/6.

Fig. 5. Characteristic parameters of surface roughness of samples: (a) R_a and (b) R_z .

Fig. 6. MAO coating thicknesses (a) ZrN coating; (b) ZrN/MAO/2; (c) ZrN/MAO/4; (d) Zr La1 mapping of the ZrN/MAO/4 sample; (e) ZrN/MAO/6 and (f) Zr La1 mapping of the ZrN/MAO/6 sample.

Table 1
Thickness of sample coatings.

Sample	MAO-coating (μm)		PVD-coating (μm)	
	inner layer	outer layer	Ti adhesion layer	ZrN layer
ZrN	-	-	0.4 ± 0.1	4.5 ± 0.1
ZrN/MAO/2	1.2 ± 0.29	3.2 ± 0.53	-	-
ZrN/MAO/4	1.1 ± 0.17	9.0 ± 0.52	-	-
ZrN/MAO/6	1.3 ± 0.14	14.1 ± 0.92	-	-

9). Thus, the presence of this phase can positively influence the corrosion and mechanical properties of the coating, including a possible photocatalytic effect [22]. In all MAO coating samples, the intermetallic phase AlSi_3Ti_2 was present, confirming that the discharge occurred on the surface of the Ti6Al4V substrate during the process with the distribution of the fused components through discharge channels.

1 - ZrN; 2 - ZrSiO₄; 3 - Zr_nO_m; 4 - ZrTiO₄;
5 - TiO₂(Rutile); 6 - TiO₂(Anatase); 7 - AlSi₃Ti₂

Fig. 7. XRPD patterns of MAO coatings on ZrN under different MAO process conditions.

(5)

(6)

(7)

The surface analysis by XPS showed (Fig. 8) the presence of different bond types and oxidation states of the elements in the ZrN coating deposited on the Ti6Al4V substrate. The analysis performed took into account the original surface without the use of ion bombardment. The results of the C1s peak indicate the presence of adsorbed impurities, including C-C (284.85 eV), C-H (284.85 eV), C-OH (286.25 eV), C-O-C (286.25 eV), and O=C-O (288.41 eV) bonds. The XPS spectrum of N1s

Fig. 8. XPS analysis of ZrN coating before Ar sputtering.

corresponds to the dominant ZrN peak at position 396.8 eV. The presence of oxynitride (395.4 eV) can be observed from the oxygen contamination present. A peak with a binding energy of 399.5 eV (N-O) was reported by Suda et al. [23]. XPS spectra of Zr 3d show two peaks at 181.7 eV and 184.1 eV, the binding energy values for the two duplets correspond to ZrO_2 (3d-5/2) and ZrO_2 (3d-3/2) [24]. The presence of SiO_2 , which ranges from 103.2 - 106.4 eV (Si2p), can be confirmed by BE [25,26]. In addition to the oxide form of zirconium, the presence of ZrN was identified at positions 179.5 eV (3d-3/2) and 181.9 (3d-3/2). It is also necessary to mention the oxygen spectrum of O1s present, where at position 531.5 eV, there is oxygen originating from O-H bond contamination, and at position 529.5 eV, there is oxygen from ZrO_2 and ZrO_xN_y bonds [27].

In order to remove impurities in the form of an elemental representation of carbon and oxygen, ion bombardment was carried out for 5 min. To eliminate inhomogeneous elemental representation, two regions on the analysed sample were selected. The presence of the C 1s peak in the XPS spectrum (Fig. 9) indicates the possible presence of carbonate compounds that have been decomposed from the electrolyte into low molecular weight hydrocarbons (C-C, C-O) and could thus become part of the MAO coating surface by sorption mechanisms. The binding energy (BE) of O 1s corresponds to the presence of metal oxides, which corresponds to the binding energies of Ti and Zr oxides. These elements are in a tetravalent oxidation state and are likely to be the existence of TiO_2 (anatase or rutile) and ZrO_2 phases, but may also be binary ZrO_2-TiO_2 and ZrO_2-SiO_2 systems in the presence of crystalline $ZrTiO_4$ and $ZrSiO_4$ from the reaction of ZrO_2 with amorphous SiO_2 present [28,29]. The presence of SiO_2 , which ranges from 103.2 - 106.4 eV (Si2p), can be confirmed by BE. Depending on the absence of crystalline SiO_2 in the XRD record (Fig. 7), it is possible to confirm the presence of amorphous SiO_2 formed during the cooling of the ceramic layer [30]. The BE shifts are due to sample inhomogeneity and differential charging, mainly manifested in Zr, Si, and Ti oxides due to different Pauling's electronegativities. Changes in the chemical states on the surface of the samples can occur with the formation of simple oxides or complex oxide phases, as indicated in the XRD record; this fact suggests that the Zr, Si and Ti atoms become more charged [31].

3.3. MAO surface wettability and corrosion resistance

The wettability results characterised by the contact angle are shown for the substrate, ZrN and MAO coating samples in Fig. 10. The ZrN film deposited on the Ti6Al4V substrate exhibits weakly hydrophobic properties, which are related to both the roughness of the coating (Fig. 5) and the low electronegativity of Zr [32]. In general, it is known that the MAO technique allows the preparation of highly hydrophilic surfaces [33] related to the key roughness parameters achieved in terms of surface wettability [34]. MAO coatings prepared on the hydrophobic PVD layer of ZrN exhibited hydrophilic properties. The contact angle results (Fig. 10) show an increase in the contact angle related to the applied source frequency. This aspect also has a significant effect on the

Fig. 10. Wettability of substrate, ZrN coating and MAO coatings.

development of roughness (Fig. 2), which is correlated with the increase in contact angle for ZrN/MAO/4 and ZrN/MAO/6 samples. An increase in the variance of values related to layer heterogeneity was also observed for both samples. The presence of micro/macro pores in the coating related to the formation of capillary effect may also have contributed to the decrease in contact angle mainly observed for the ZrN/MAO/2 sample [35]. Based on the ANOVA Tukey test, it was found that a statistically insignificant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed in terms of the contact angle between ZrN/MAO/4 and ZrN/MAO/6 samples. The same result was obtained when comparing these two samples and substrates. Thus, it can be concluded that the resulting surface inhomogeneities in ZrN/MAO/4 and ZrN/MAO/6 samples affect the resulting hydrophilic effect of MAO surfaces.

Potentiodynamic polarization curves describing the corrosion behaviour of the different types of coatings, including the substrate, are shown in Fig. 11. The calculated corrosion parameters from Tafel extrapolation include electrochemical corrosion potential (E_{corr}) and corrosion current density (I_{corr}) and are summarised in Table 2. From the comparison of E_{corr} values, it is evident that the increase in corrosion resistance is correlated with the coating prepared with the highest source frequency applied and the highest coating thickness achieved (Table 2). This aspect of ZrN/MAO/6 sample preparation also increased surface roughness (Fig. 5) and coating porosity [36]. The increase in E_{corr} and I_{corr} for the ZrN/MAO/6 specimen compared to the ZrN coating and substrate indicates the effect of surface roughness, porosity and the presence of surface defects (cracks) as well as the presence of an active surface which is exposed to corrosion processes. If the MAO coatings are degraded mechanically or electrochemically during its lifespan, the surface of substrate will be exposed to corrosion environment. Therefore there also were the corrosion properties of substrate presented in this paper indicating very low corrosion rate and thus significantly reduced risk of further corrosion degradation of it. It is the presence of surface defects, of which there are probably more in the case of the ZrN/MAO/2

Fig. 9. XPS analysis of MAO coating after Ar sputtering: (a) ZrN/MAO/02; (b) ZrN/MAO/04; (c) ZrN/MAO/06.

Fig. 11. Potentiodynamic polarisation curves of Ti6Al4V; ZrN coating; MAO coatings.

Table 2

Parameters characterising the corrosion behaviour of the MAO coating.

Sample	E_{corr} (mV)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)
Ti6Al4V	12	0.04
ZrN	-26	0.03
ZrN/MAO/2	-388	3.28
ZrN/MAO/4	-431	2.52
ZrN/MAO/6	234	0.89

and ZrN/MAO/4 samples, that leads to the formation of hydrated Ti/Zr oxides - $\text{Ti}_x\text{O}_y(\text{H}_2\text{O})_z$ - containing a proportion of Ti-OH groups. The formation of hydrated oxides may be aided by the passage of an electric current when connected to the electrode during corrosion experiments. It is likely that in aqueous solution with contains of chlorides, the soluble chlorides are formed from hydrated Ti/Zr oxides and subsequently complex TiCl_6^{3-} or ZrCl_6^{3-} anions may also be formed [37].

The surface roughness is related to both the MAO process time and the selected source frequency. The importance in terms of corrosion resistance is mainly related to the quality of the inner compact layer. The increase in surface roughness, according to Li et al. [38], however, also indicates an improvement in the strength of the coating/substrate bond and effective retardation of the propagation of corrosion attack to form degradation products.

3.4. Tribological behaviour of hybrid ceramic oxide layer

Two configurations of the tribometers were used to test the tribological properties. In the first case, a rotating pin-on-disc characterised a uniform movement with constant speed. In the second case, a linear pin-on-disc measured a dynamic change in speed, which changes from zero at the dead centre point and reaches maximum speed in the middle of the track. During the rotational mode test (Fig. 12a), the friction coefficient of the ZrN coating stabilised after a short running-in period of around 0.55 to 0.65. It was significantly higher than the CoF of the Ti6Al4V base material. The CoF of ZrN/MAO/2 increased significantly after approximately 800 cycles. After roughly 4000 cycles, the coating completely collapsed, and the CoF decreased to the same level as in the case of the uncoated base material Ti6Al4V. ZrN/MAO/2 had the smallest thickness (Table 1), and its fastest wear on the base material can be expected. The ZrN/MAO/4 and ZrN/MAO/6 samples had the most stable courses of friction coefficients, which performed very similarly, and their CoF stabilised around 0.4 to 0.45.

The friction coefficient courses during the tests performed on the linear tribometer (Fig. 12b) were similar to those measured on the rotation tribometer (Fig. 12a). However, a significant difference is the fact that the wear track of the ZrN/MAO/2 sample did not penetrate through the coating on the Ti6Al4V base material. The high values and fluctuation of the friction coefficient for ZrN samples (Fig. 13) can be

Fig. 12. Course of the friction coefficient in a) rotational and b) linear mode.

Fig. 13. 3D profiles and cross sections of wear tracks for samples: (a) Ti6Al4V; (b) ZrN; (c) ZrN/MAO/2; (d) ZrN/MAO/4; (e) ZrN/MAO/6.

attributed to the presence of Zr macroparticles in the coating from CAE deposition [39]. In the case of Ti6Al4V, the friction coefficient instabilities can be caused by the periodic adhesion contacts between the ball and the substrate, which are visible in Fig. 13. If we compare the shapes of the wear tracks for linear mode in Fig. 13, we can see that in

the case of the ZrN/MAO/2 sample (Fig. 13c), the wear track has a sharp shape, indicating that there has been penetration up to the inner layer. Unlike the ZrN/MAO/4 (Fig. 13d) and ZrN/MAO/6 (Fig. 13e) samples, where friction still took place in the outer layer.

From the perspective of specific wear rate (Fig. 14), the test results

Fig. 14. Comparison of specific wear rates on a linear and rotary tribometer.

on both tribometers were similar, with the exception of the ZrN/MAO/2 coating, which showed the lowest specific wear rate of all MAO samples in the linear test. During the rotation test, its wear was the highest because it had broken through the coating on the Ti6Al4V base material. For a correct comparison of the specific wear rate, it would be necessary to test coatings with a comparable thickness. It can be expected that, in a longer linear test, the breakdown would also occur significantly earlier than for the other tested coatings. The primary mode of wear for all coatings was abrasion (Fig. 15). In general, MAO coatings showed significantly lower wear than the Ti6Al4V base material but higher wear than ZrN.

Friction and abrasion of ZrN MAO coatings can be affected by components based on Ti and Zr oxides (Fig. 7). The ZrSiO₄ component improves wear resistance but increases the friction coefficient [40]. In contrast, the ZrTiO₄ component improves wear [41] and reduces the friction coefficient [42]. Therefore, a synergistic effect of these components can be assumed.

3.5. Adhesion of the oxide layer

The unmodified ZrN coating experienced a significant spallation failure after reaching a critical load of 22 N (Fig. 16a). The ZrN MAO coated samples (Fig. 16b, 16c and 16d) did not show failure in adhesion to the coating; however, all of these samples experienced crack formation within the scratch track at a load of approximately 18 N. Both recorded failure modes of coatings are typical for coating on a ductile substrate [43]. Although the scratch test method is unsuitable for testing

Fig. 16. Scratch test of (a) ZrN; (b) ZrN/MAO/2; (c) ZrN/MAO/4 and (d) ZrN/MAO/6 coatings (load 1-30 N).

coatings on a ductile Ti6Al4V substrate, the adhesion of ZrN MAO coatings can be considered very good. The coatings exhibited similar or better adhesion than those of MAO coatings of comparable thickness prepared on metal substrates [44].

4. Conclusions

The preparation of hybrid layers in conjunction with PVD coatings and MAO technology enables the controlled removal of defects associated with the surface modification of implants from the Ti6Al4V alloy. In the case of ZrN coatings, the use of MAO led to a structural phase transformation to form an oxide layer with altered corrosion and tribological properties. Achieving these aspects thus allows using these hybrid coatings primarily in orthopaedic applications due to the increased adhesion to the base material Ti6Al4V compared to the ZrN coating while achieving higher corrosion resistance. The best improvement of these properties was achieved for the ZrN/MAO/6 sample. For its preparation, a source frequency of 222 Hz was used, which allowed the elimination of coating defects and the size of the active surface that was exposed to corrosion attack. At the same time, it can be concluded that the MAO treatment led to the desired higher surface wettability, which, in addition to the chemical composition and topography, positively influences the metal-cell interaction in the realisation of these coatings. The tribological properties were influenced by the formation of Zr and Ti oxide-based components. The major identified coating phases include ZrSiO₄ and ZrTiO₄. The ZrSiO₄ component increased wear resistance, and the ZrTiO₄ component reduced the friction coefficient

Fig. 15. Abrasive friction between a) ZrN/MAO/6 sample and b) Al₂O₃ ball after tribological test in rotational mode.

and stabilised its course.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Roman Gabor: Conceptualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Project administration, Writing – original draft, Funding acquisition. **Ladislav Cvrček:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Marie Kudrnová:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Josef Hlinka:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing – original draft. **Marek Večeř:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Visualization. **Matěj Buřil:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jan Walter:** Methodology, Investigation. **Miha Čekada:** Methodology, Investigation. **Aljaž Drnovšek:** Methodology, Investigation. **Petr Unucka:** Methodology, Investigation. **Kateřina Mamulová Kutláková:** Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Oldřich Motyka:** Methodology, Investigation. **Jana Seidlerová:** Supervision, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

This paper was created as part of the project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004631. Materials and technologies for sustainable development within the Jan Amos Komenský Operational Program financed by the European Union and from the state budget of the Czechia. This paper was created as part of the project of the Grant Agency of the Czech Technical University in Prague, grant No. SGS22/107/OHK2/2T/12.

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